

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Assessing Personal Hygiene Practices of Food Handlers in and Around a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Cross-Sectional Study in Sonitpur District of Assam

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 21 Feb 2026

Keywords:

Food handlers, personal hygiene, food safety, knowledge, practice

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18726473

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Food borne diseases are one of the most frequent public health problems. Food safety is major public health concern, particularly in developing countries where foodborne diseases remain common. Food handlers' personal hygiene habits are essential for preventing food contamination and the spread of illnesses. In addition to human cost, poor hygiene contributes to significant economic burdens due to productivity losses & health care expenses. Food handlers play an important role in ensuring food safety and wellbeing of consumers. Food handlers working in and around healthcare institutions require special attention as they cater to vulnerable populations. The aim of the study was to assess the personal hygiene practices of food handlers in and around a tertiary care hospital in Sonitpur district of Assam. **Material and Methods:** A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among food handlers working in food establishments in and around Tezpur Medical College and Hospital, Sonitpur district, Assam. The study was carried out over a period of three months from September to November 2024. A total of 103 food handlers were selected using purposive sampling methods. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews using a pre-designed, pre-tested questionnaire assessing sociodemographic profile, knowledge, personal hygiene practices. Data were entered and analysed using MS Excel and presented in tabular forms. **Results:** Majority of the participants (83.49%) belonged to the 18–40 years age group, with males constituting 80.58%. Nearly 37.8% of respondents were illiterate. Knowledge regarding hygienic food storage was present in 75.7% of participants, while 62.13% had knowledge of proper food handling. About 68.85% maintained physical hygiene during food preparation, but only 55.55% did so consistently in institutional settings. Only 36.89% had received formal training regarding food hygiene. More than half of respondents lacked knowledge about disease transmission through dirty hands. A considerable proportion reported recent illnesses such as diarrhoea, flu-like symptoms

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

eczema. Conclusion: Although personal hygiene practices were satisfactory among many food handlers, significant gaps existed in knowledge and training. Regular health education and certification programs are essential to improve food safety and prevent foodborne diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Food safety is a vital aspect of public health, especially in healthcare settings where individuals are more vulnerable to infections. Food handlers' personal hygiene habits are a key component among the many variables affecting food safety. Food handlers are directly involved in the preparation, processing, distribution, and storage of food, and the microbiological quality of food can be greatly impacted by their hygiene-related practices. Poor personal hygiene of food handlers may lead to food contamination, thereby increasing the risk of food-borne diseases among consumers [1,2]. Food-borne diseases remain one of the most frequent public health problems encountered in daily life worldwide. These illnesses result from the consumption of food contaminated with pathogenic microorganisms, toxins, or chemical substances, many of which can be introduced by improper handling practices. Poor hand hygiene among food handlers has been repeatedly linked to outbreaks of food-borne infections. Additional personal hygiene factors that increase the risk of contamination during food preparation and serving include dirty clothes, untrimmed nails, exposed hair, and inadequate wound or cut care [3].

Food-borne illnesses have a substantial financial impact on people, families, and healthcare systems in addition to the direct human cost of illness. Food-borne diseases in hospitals can result in longer hospital stays, more antibiotic use, and more diagnostic and treatment procedure [4]. Tertiary care hospitals are complicated settings where a wide range of people, including inpatients, outpatients, medical staff, attendants, and guests,

are provided a lot of food every day. Food services in and around these hospitals may include central kitchens, ward pantries, staff cafeterias, and external food vendors. The variability in food handling settings and the involvement of multiple categories of food handlers increase the likelihood of inconsistent hygiene practices[5]. Personal hygiene practices encompass a range of behaviours aimed at minimizing contamination of food by harmful microorganisms. These include regular and correct handwashing, maintaining clean and appropriate work attire, keeping fingernails trimmed and clean, covering hair adequately, and refraining from food handling during illness. In healthcare settings, where the threshold for infection is lower, even minimal lapses in hygiene can have serious consequences [6]. Foodhandlers role is especially important in hospitals since infection prevention and control strategies are strongly related to food safety. Unsafe food can act as a vehicle for pathogens, contributing to hospital-associated infections that undermine patient recovery and increase healthcare costs. Therefore, assessing and improving personal hygiene practices among food handlers should be regarded as an integral component of patient safety and quality of care [7].

Despite the recognized importance of food handler hygiene, gaps often exist between knowledge and practice. Factors such as inadequate training, lack of supervision, heavy workload, insufficient facilities for handwashing, and limited access to protective clothing can negatively affect compliance with hygiene standards. Identifying these gaps through systematic assessment is essential for implementing effective corrective measures [8,9]. Kassa H, et. al; 2010, focused on evaluating personal hygiene practices among food handlers provides evidence necessary for informed decision-making and policy development. In and around tertiary care hospitals, this research gains

added importance because it addresses both community and hospital-based food safety concerns. [10,11]. Assessing personal hygiene practices also contributes to raising awareness among food handlers about their responsibility in preventing disease transmission and adopt safe practices. In hospital settings, such a culture aligns with broader goals of infection control and patient-centred care [12]. Given the vulnerability of hospital populations and the complexity of food service systems in these settings, regular evaluation of hygiene practices is necessary to identify risks and implement effective preventive strategies. Strengthening personal hygiene among food handlers ultimately supports safer food, protects public health, and enhances the quality of healthcare delivery [13].

OBJECTIVE

The aim of the study was to assess the personal hygiene practices of food handlers in and around a tertiary care hospital in Sonitpur district of Assam, with the specific objectives of evaluating the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among food handlers and assessing their personal hygiene practices.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This community based cross-sectional study was conducted among food handlers working in food establishments in and around Tezpur Medical College and Hospital, Tezpur, Assam from 1st September 2024 to 30th November 2024 (for a period of 3 months).

The study population comprised food handlers working in various food establishments including hotels, restaurants, hostels, street vending units, and institutional kitchens located in and around Tezpur Medical College and Hospital, Sonitpur district, Assam. Inclusion criteria included food

handlers who were present at the time of the study and provided informed consent. The exclusion criteria were: (1) Food handlers unavailable at the time of the study, and (2) those unwilling to participate.

A sample size of 103 was selected through purposive sampling. Ethical considerations: Ethical approval has been obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of Tezpur Medical College and Hospital, Tezpur, Assam.

Data collection was done through a predesigned and pretested interview schedule. Sections included information pertaining to socio demographic profile, knowledge levels, attitude and practices obtained by predesigned pretested schedule. Written informed consent was taken after explaining the purpose of the study.

Collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using descriptive statistical methods. Frequencies and percentages were calculated to summarize sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge levels, and hygiene practices of food handlers, where necessary tabulation of results was done. Results were not subjected to any form of inferential statistic, as the nature of the study was exploratory.

RESULTS

A total of 103 respondents were included in the study, the majority of whom belonged to the 18–40-year age group, accounting for 86 individuals (83.49%). Participants aged 18 years or younger comprised 11 respondents (10.68%), while those older than 40 years formed the smallest group with 6 respondents (5.82%), indicating a clear predominance of young adults in the study population. Out of the 103 respondents, the majority were males, accounting for 80.58% (83), while females constituted 19.42% (20). This

indicates a clear male predominance among food handlers in the study population. Nearly half of the respondents 47 (45.6%) had an education level below the 10th standard, while 39 (37.8%) were illiterate. Only 17 (16.5%) of the food handlers had completed education up to the 10th standard, indicating an overall low educational status. The majority of respondents 61 (59.22%) were food handlers from hotels and restaurants. This was followed by those from institutional settings 27 (26.21%), while street vendors constitute 15 (14.5%) of the study population.

Only 36.89% of respondents reported having undergone training or certification related to proper food preparation. In contrast, a substantial majority (63.10%) had not received any formal training in food preparation practices. The majority of respondents demonstrated knowledge about hygienic food storage, accounting for 75.7% of the study population. In contrast, 11.6% reported having no knowledge, while 12.6% were uncertain about proper food storage practices. A majority of respondents (62.13%) reported having knowledge regarding proper food handling practices. However, 7.76% indicated no knowledge, while a substantial proportion (30.11%) were uncertain about appropriate food handling. 30% had knowledge about transmission of disease by dirty hands. Majority of the

respondents believed that proper handwashing during preparation reduces food borne illness which constitute 70.2%, those aware that cooked food be stored properly covered constitute 68%. Respondents who were aware that food handlers is an important source of food borne illness were 61%, while those who consider food stall be kept clean were 54%.

Majority (71.2%) of the respondents washed hands before handling food, while 63.4% washed hands after handling waste. 96.2% respondents bath regularly, while 70.1% used to regularly wash their clothes. Only half of the respondents (53.2%) used to wear gloves and apron before food preparation, while 65.3% keep finger nails trimmed and clean, and 82.1% of respondents properly store and cover food after preparation. Most respondents (68.85%) reported maintaining physical hygiene during food preparation and handling in hotels and restaurants. More than half of the respondents (55.55%) reported maintaining physical hygiene during food preparation and handling in institutional settings. Respondents (53.39%) reported flu-like illness in the last three months, while 29.12% suffered from diarrhoea and 18.4% from eczema. These findings suggest a notable burden of hygiene-related illnesses among the food handlers.

Table 1: Socio demographic characteristics of food handlers (n=103)

Variable	Category	Frequency (%)
Gender	Male	83 (80.58%)
	Female	20 (19.42%)
Age in years	<18	11 (10.68%)
	18-40	86 (83.49 %)
	>40	6 (5.82%)
Educational qualifications	<10 th	47 (45.6%)
	10 th pass	17 (16.5%)
	illiterate	39 (37.8%)
Type of food handlers	Hotels and restaurants	61 (59.22%)
	Institutional settings	27 (26.2%)
	Street vendors	15 (14.5%)
Training received regarding proper food handling	Yes	38 (36.89%)
	No	65 (63.10%)

Table 2: Knowledge of food handlers regarding food safety:

Knowledge questions	No of response	Percentage
Aware about storage of food	78	75.7%
Knowledge about proper food handling	64	62.13%
Knowledge about diseases transmission through dirty hands	31	30%

Table 3: Attitude of food handlers on food hygiene

Attitude statements	No of respondents	Percentage
Believed that proper handwashing during preparation reduces food borne illness	73	70.2%
Aware cooked food should be stored properly covered	70	68%
Aware that food handlers is an important source of food borne illness	63	61%
Consider food stall must be kept clean.	56	54%

Table 4: Practice of food handlers on food hygiene:

Practice parameters	No of respondents	Percentage
Hand washing before handling food	73	71.2%
Hand washing after handling waste	65	63.4%
Regular bathing	99	96.2%
Regular washing of clothes	72	70.1%
Use of gloves and apron before food preparation	55	53.2%
Finger nails kept clean and trimmed	67	65.3%
Proper storage and covering of food after preparation	84	82.1%

DISCUSSION

The present study assessed personal hygiene practices and knowledge among food handlers working in and around a tertiary care hospital in Sonitpur district, Assam. Patil SR, et. al; 2005, highlighted both encouraging practices and significant gaps that require public health attention. The majority of food handlers belonged to the economically productive age group of 18–40 years, similar to findings reported in studies conducted in other parts of India. This indicates that young adults form the backbone of the food service workforce [14]. A predominance of male food handlers was observed in the study, which aligns with several Indian studies where food handling is largely male-dominated, especially in hotels, restaurants, and street vending sectors. Educational status of participants revealed that a considerable proportion were illiterate or educated below the secondary level. Low educational attainment may limit understanding of food safety

principles and hygiene practices, emphasizing the importance of simple, practical training programs [15,16].

Knowledge regarding hygienic food storage was present in nearly three-fourths of the respondents, which is a positive finding. However, a notable proportion either lacked knowledge or were uncertain, indicating inconsistent awareness levels. Knowledge about proper food handling was comparatively lower, suggesting that while food handlers may recognize the importance of storage, they may not fully understand safe handling procedures during preparation and serving [17]. Maintenance of physical hygiene during food preparation was reported by about two-thirds of respondents. However, hygiene practices were poorer in institutional settings, where only slightly more than half maintained adequate hygiene. This is concerning, given the higher risk associated with institutional food services catering to vulnerable populations. The discrepancy between knowledge

and practice observed in the study may be due to lack of supervision, workload, or inadequate facilities [18]. Training status emerged as a critical gap, with nearly two-thirds of food handlers having no formal training or certification. Similar findings have been reported in studies from Kolkata, and other regions, highlighting a nationwide issue of public health concern. Lack of training limits awareness about critical aspects such as hand hygiene, cross-contamination, and disease transmission, thereby increasing the risk of foodborne illnesses [19].

Knowledge regarding disease transmission through dirty hands was particularly poor, with more than half of the respondents unaware of this basic concept. Mubyazi GM, et. al; 2013, underscored the urgent need for health education focusing on hand hygiene, which is one of the most effective measures to prevent food contamination [20]. Todd EC. 2014, revealed that a significant proportion of food handlers reported illnesses such as diarrhoea, influenza-like symptoms, and eczema in the preceding three months. These conditions may not only affect the health of food handlers but also pose a risk of transmitting infections to consumers if proper hygiene is not maintained [21]. Taha S, et. al; 2021, indicated that while some food handlers demonstrate satisfactory hygiene practices, major gaps remain in knowledge, training, and consistent application of hygienic measures. Strengthening regulatory enforcement, ensuring periodic medical examinations, and providing regular training programs can substantially improve food safety standards [22].

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that although the personal hygiene practices of food handlers around the tertiary care hospital were generally adequate, significant deficiencies exist in knowledge,

training, and awareness regarding disease transmission and hand hygiene. The lack of formal training among the majority of food handlers is a major concern. Regular health education, mandatory certification programs, and continuous monitoring are essential to improve hygiene practices, prevent food contamination, and reduce the risk of foodborne diseases in the community.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The authors thank the study participants and the staff of the Department of Community Medicine, Tezpur Medical College, for their cooperation and support during the conduct of this study.

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HOW TO CITE: Dr. Rupali Baruah, Dr. Dipul Swargiary, Assessing Personal Hygiene Practices of Food Handlers in and Around a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Cross-Sectional Study in Sonitpur District of Assam, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2026, Vol 4, Issue 2, 3602-3609. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18726473>

